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Research Article

**THE AWARENESS OF COLORECTAL CANCER AND ITS
RISK FACTORS IN MADINAH: A CROSS SECTIONAL
STUDY**

Waleed E. Almalki MD, Hazim A. Alzhoufi MD, Muath A. Altwaijry MD,
Abdulrahman M. Dad MD, Owais K. Khoshhal MD
Taibah University, College of Medicine, Madinah 41411, Saudi Arabia

Abstract:

Background: This study will help create a more targeted education and screening programs in order to raise the awareness of Colorectal Cancer (CRC) and its risk factors, through assessing the knowledge about CRC, its risk factors and screening in the population of Madinah, which will be reflected by a decrease in its incidence.

Methodology: The study designed as a cross-sectional study, took place in Madinah. Participants were approached by a 25 multiple choice questions survey about CRC. Results were analyzed according to demographic data to determine different levels of knowledge and number of risk factors.

Results: Of 385 participants, more than half were male. 18-29 years old 44.2% and undergraduate or above 54%. On the knowledge score, the highest score by the participants was 8, 53.4% got 2 or 3. At least 64.3% of the participant has 2 or 3 risk factors of CRC. The most common risk factor found is eating red meat 61.5%. About 69.1% didn't hear about CRC screening. People at the age of CRC risk were not advised by their doctor to undergo CRC screening were 75.9%.

Conclusion: Overall, the knowledge about CRC in Madinah is poor. The higher the education level and higher income related to have more knowledge and more chance to hear about CRC screening. With the increase in financial income and education level there is a decrease in the number of CRC risk factors, the opposite was found in relation to age. We recommend creating an educational and screening program for CRC.

Keywords: Colorectal cancer, awareness, risk factors, screening, Madinah

Corresponding author:

Waleed E. Almalki, MD "Saudi Arabia"

Taibah University, College of Medicine

P.O.Box: 344

Zip Code: 41411

Madinah, Saudi Arabia

Contact No.: +966567070766, Email: wm1416@gmail.com

QR code

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INTRODUCTION:

Colorectal Cancer (CRC) is the third most common malignancy in males and the second most common malignancy in females worldwide[1]. In Saudi Arabia, CRC is the second most common malignancy, which is considered as the most common type of cancer in males 10.6% of Saudi population, and the third in females by 8.9%[2]. CRC is associated with several risk factors such as age above 40, family history of CRC or colorectal polyps, physical inactivity, smoking, and alcohol consumption.[3] A previous study about risk factors of CRC in Saudi Arabia showed that a positive family history of CRC and physical inactivity were the most common risk factors associated with CRC.[4] In 2015, the World Health Organization (WHO) reported that 774,000 deaths worldwide are caused by CRC[5]. In Saudi Arabia, the mortality rate of CRC is 8.3%[6]. There are no previous studies that have investigated the awareness and the risk factors of CRC in the population of Madinah in comparison to other studies were done in other regions of Saudi Arabia like Riyadh and Jeddah. This study aims to assess the CRC awareness, prevalence of risk factors in the population of Madinah. The results of this study will help in creating a more targeted education and screening programs in order to raise the awareness of CRC and its risk factors which will be reflected by a decrease in the incidence of CRC in Madinah.

Research objectives:

1. To assess the awareness of CRC symptoms, risk factors and screening in the population of Madinah.
2. To identify the prevalence of risk factors known to be associated with CRC in the population of Madinah.

METHODS:**Setting:**

The study took place in Madinah, Saudi Arabia during the period from November 2017 to August 2018. Madinah population is 2,080,436 (year 2016), about 15.5% are above age of 50 years[6].

Study design:

The study designed as a cross-sectional study.

Study population and sampling:

The calculated sample of this study is 384 participants following the parameters of 95% confident level, 50% expected frequency and design effect 1.0, were interviewed in various Primary Health Care centers (Al-Khalediya, Al-Aziziyah, Al-Nasr, Al-Salaam, Al-Duwaimah, Al-Hurrah Al-Sharqyah and Security Forces Hospital) in Madinah. The inclusion criteria for this study is people aged above 18 and living in Madinah. Exclusion criteria

were people who have been diagnosed with CRC or are living outside of Madinah.

Sampling technique:

The collection of the sample was done using a multi-stage sampling technique, divided into two stages:

Stage 1: Selection of 7 primary health care centers using a simple random technique from the list of all primary health care centers in Madinah.

Stage 2: In each center, every patient who has an odd number according to clinic order was interviewed, the selection done through a systematic random technique.

Collection of data done on 3 days during morning working hours, and another 3 days during night working hours each week.

Data collection and measurements:

Data collected through interview questionnaires consisting of 25 questions that assess the awareness of CRC, regarding knowledge, its risk factors and symptoms. Of these, 4 questions were obtained from a survey of Zubaidi et al.[7] which discussed the awareness of CRC in Saudi Arabia All questions were validated according to Cancer Awareness Measure (CAM). All questions are multiple choice questions written in the Arabic language in a standard format. The incidence of CRC in Madinah investigated using data obtained from the Saudi Cancer Registry (SCR).

Pilot study:

A pilot study conducted in Taibah University using 30 participants.

Data management and analysis plan:

Statistical analysis performed using Microsoft EXCEL 2016 and SPSS 24, data presented as numbers, percentages, tables and charts.

Ethical consideration and approval:

Informed consent obtained from every participant. Data considered confidential and for research use only. Ethical Approval has been obtained from the Ethical Committee at Taibah University and Institutional Review Board (IRB), General Directorate of Health Affairs in Madinah.

RESULTS:

The sample of the study comprised 385 participants out of 420 invited to participate, giving a response rate of 91.7%. 35 were excluded because they are not living in Madinah (n=16) or didn't complete the questionnaire (n=19). The general characteristics of the respondents are shown in Table1. They were 56% (n=214) males and 44% (n=171) females. Most of the respondents were 18-29 years old 44.2%, undergraduate or above 54%, and married 67.3%.

Table 1. Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Characteristic	No. (N=385)	Percent
Age		
18-29	170	44.2%
39-30	124	32.2%
40-49	62	16.1%
>50	29	7.5%
Sex		
Male	214	55.6%
Female	171	44.4%
Marital Status		
Single	109	28.3%
Married	259	67.3%
Divorced / Widowed	17	4.4%
Education		
Elementary	18	4.7%
Intermediate	19	4.9%
High school	140	36.4%
Undergraduate and above	208	54.0%
Financial Situation		
< 5000 SR	150	39.0%
5000 - 10000 SR	151	39.2%
10000 - 20000 SR	71	18.4%
> 20000 SR	13	3.4%

Among participants with “undergraduate or above” level of education, 84.1% (n=175) had heard about CRC compared to 70.7% (n=99) among those with high school education (P=.002). According to the financial income, people whose income was > 20000 SR 100% (n=13) heard about CRC while those with an income < 5000 SR 74.0% (n=111) heard of it (P=.036).

The majority of participants (78.5%) didn't know that CRC is the second most common cancer in Saudi Arabia. The undergraduate or above participants (75%) (n=156) didn't answer correctly, the same for the elementary level of education (94.5%) (n=17). Regarding the financial income, 53.9% (n=7) of whom their income > 20000 SR didn't get the right answer, were 84.7% (n=127) of whom their income < 5000 SR didn't get the right answer (P=.014).

Knowledge

The knowledge was assessed by 9 questions containing 28 items that covered certain aspects of CRC including awareness, risk factors and screening; 22 of these items were true, the others were either wrong answers or "I Don't Know" (Table 2). The maximum score to get is 22 and the lowest is zero. The highest score by the participants was 8, while the lowest was 1. Over half of the participants (53.4%) got a score of 2 or 3.

According to the participants perception of their knowledge about CRC, causes, risk factors and treatment, the results showed that 44.4% (n=171) poor, 35.6% (n=137) low, 19.2% (n=74) good, and 0.8% (n=3) excellent.

Regarding where the participants had heard about CRC, 21% (n=81) had never heard about CRC.

Figure 1. Knowledge of CRC signs and symptoms

Most of the sample 71% (n=276) didn't know that CRC is more common in males. The majority of male and female didn't know that CRC is more common in males 80.4% (n=172), 60.8% (n=104) respectively (P=.000). People whose income was > 20000 SR knew that CRC is more in male 61.5% (n=8), were 18.7% (n=28) of whom their income < 5000 SR didn't get the right answer (P=.001).

Regarding the signs and symptoms of CRC, most of the respondents chose continuous abdominal pain 52.5% (n=202), while 0.8% (n=3) thought that CRC had no signs or symptoms (the detailed responses shown in Figure 1).

Most of the participants chose Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD), smoking and personal or family history of CRC as risk factors of CRC (Figure 2)

Table 2. Participants Knowledge on CRC

Figure 2. Participants Knowledge of CRC Risk factors

Questions		Sex				P Value
		Male		Female		
		Number	Percent	Number	Percent	
Have you ever heard about CRC?	No	48	22.4%	32	18.7%	.373
	Yes	166	77.6%	139	81.3%	
How widespread is CRC in Saudi Arabia?	The most widespread	17	7.9%	12	7.0%	.298
	The second most widespread	47	22.0%	35	20.5%	
	The third most widespread	35	16.4%	18	10.5%	
	I don't know	115	53.7%	106	62.0%	
CRC is more in:	Men	42	19.6%	67	39.2%	.000
	Women	27	12.6%	8	4.7%	
	Equal in Men and Women	58	27.1%	31	18.1%	
	I don't know	87	40.7%	65	38.0%	
CRC considered to be:	Inherited	14	6.5%	15	8.8%	.230
	Acquired	56	26.2%	54	31.6%	
	Inherited and Acquired	72	33.6%	42	24.6%	
	I don't know	72	33.6%	60	35.1%	
CRC Signs and Symptoms						
Bleeding from Rectum	Chose	103	48.1%	61	35.7%	.014
Blood in Stool	Chose	110	51.4%	67	39.2%	.017
Change in Bowel Habits	Chose	88	41.1%	46	26.9%	.004
Continuous Abdominal Pain	Chose	112	52.3%	90	52.6%	.954
Unreasonable Weight Loss	Chose	77	36.0%	50	29.2%	.162
Feeling Bloating	Chose	72	33.6%	41	24.0%	.038
Feeling of Incomplete Defecation	Chose	39	18.2%	16	9.4%	.013
Has No Symptoms	Chose	0	0.0%	3	1.8%	.052
I Don't Know	Chose	32	15.0%	35	20.5%	.156
CRC Risk Factors						
Older Age	Chose	40	18.7%	43	25.1%	.126
Personal or Family History of CRC	Chose	84	39.3%	51	29.8%	.054
Inflammatory Bowel Disease	Chose	95	44.4%	60	35.1%	.064
Obesity	Chose	45	21.0%	26	15.2%	.143
Smoking	Chose	87	40.7%	64	37.4%	.519
Eating Red Meat	Chose	38	17.8%	20	11.7%	.099
Low Physical Activity	Chose	50	23.4%	40	23.4%	.995
I Do Not Know any CRC Risk Factors	Chose	52	24.3%	58	33.9%	.038
Have you ever heard of CRC screening?	No	149	69.6%	117	68.4%	.799
	Yes	65	30.4%	54	31.6%	
At what age is CRC screening performed?	At the age of 30 years	34	15.9%	19	11.1%	.344
	At the age of 40 years	27	12.6%	21	12.3%	

	At the age of 50 years	14	6.5%	20	11.7%	
	At the presence of symptoms	38	17.8%	29	17.0%	
	I don't know	101	47.2%	82	48.0%	
CRC Screening						
FOBT	Chose	41	19.2%	36	21.1%	.644
X-Ray	Chose	15	7.0%	9	5.3%	.481
CT-Scan	Chose	29	13.6%	9	5.3%	.007
Colonoscopy	Chose	89	41.6%	89	52.0%	.041
I Do Not Know	Chose	98	45.8%	70	40.9%	.340

Table 3. Knowledge Score

Knowledge Score		
Score	Number	Percent
1	49	12.7%
2	103	26.7%
3	103	26.7%
4	68	17.6%
5	41	10.6%
6	13	3.5%
7	5	1.4%
8	3	.9%

The risk factors were assessed by 8 questions, we considered sex as a risk factor. The maximum score the participant can get is 8. The highest score was 5. 64.3% (n=248) of the participant has at least 2 or 3 risk factors for CRC. The risk factors score and its items listed in Table3. In people who aged 50 years or more 55.2% (n=16) have 3 or more risk factors compared to who aged from 18 to 29 years 44.1% (n=75), the same for male 50.7% (n=108) compared to female 38% (n=65) (P=.000).

According to the education level, 41.5% (n=86) of participants who were undergraduates or above had 3 or more risk factors, compared to 55.6% (n=10) of those with elementary education. Also the same regarding the financial income, people who had an income of > 20000 SR 30.8% (n=4) compared to who had income < 5000 SR 51.3% (n=77).

The most common risk factors found in the sample was eating red meat daily 61.5% (n=237), not doing regular physical activity 50.6% (n=195), not eating fruit and vegetable regularly 49.3% (n=190), smoking 18.4% (n=71), personal history of IBD 5.4% (n=21) and family or relative history of CRC 1.8% (n=7), there was no participant reporting to have history of CRC.

Regarding smoking, 74.4% (n=127) of those aged between 18 and 29 are not smokers, as well as 96.6% of those aged 50 years or more (n=28) (P=.008). The same relation presented in people with an income of > 20000 SR and not smoker 100% (n=13) with those with income < 5000 SR 73.3% (n=110) (P=.005)

In relation to physical activity, 45.3% (n=77) of participant aged from 18 to 29 didn't practice regular physical activity, also there is 72.4% (n=21) at the of 50 years or more didn't practice regular physical activity (P=.021). The same difference presented regarding the education level, people with an educational level of undergraduate or above and didn't practice physical activity were 42.8% (n=89), were 84.2% (n=16) of intermediate level of education didn't practice physical activity (P=.000).

People aged 50 years or more and eating red meat daily were 69% (n=20). The majority of the participants who eat red meat daily were male (70.1%; n=150) (P=.002). Regarding the financial income, 92.3% (n=12) of those with an income of > 20000 SR consume red meat, compared to 57.3% (n=86) among those with an income < 5000 SR.

On the other hand, participants aged 50 years or more 62.1% (n=18) are consuming a sufficient

amount of fruit and vegetables compared to those aged 18 to 29 years 47.6% (n=81) (P=.003).

Table 4. Participants Risk Factors

Questions		Overall		Sex				P Value
				Male		Female		
		Number	Percent	Number	Percent	Number	Percent	
Are you currently smoking?	No	314	81.77%	149	69.6%	165	96.5%	.000
	Yes	71	18.49%	65	30.4%	6	3.5%	
Do you practice regular physical activity 30 min / 5 days a week?	No	195	50.78%	107	50.0%	88	51.5%	.776
	Yes	190	49.48%	107	50.0%	83	48.5%	
Does your daily diet contain red meat?	No	148	38.54%	97	45.3%	51	29.8%	.002
	Yes	237	61.72%	117	54.7%	120	70.2%	
How many times do you eat fruit or vegetables per week?	Daily	79	20.57%	46	21.5%	33	19.3%	.283
	3-5 times / week	116	30.21%	69	32.2%	47	27.5%	
	1-2 times / week	108	28.13%	61	28.5%	47	27.5%	
	I rarely eat it weekly	82	21.35%	38	17.8%	44	25.7%	
Are you currently have inflammatory bowel disease or you have history of it?	No	364	94.79%	201	93.9%	163	95.3%	.549
	Yes	21	5.47%	13	6.1%	8	4.7%	
Are you currently have CRC or you have history of it?	No	385	100.26%	214	100.0%	171	100.0%	
	Yes	0	0%	0	0%	0	0%	
Is your father/mother, brothers/sisters, children has/have history of CRC?	No	378	98.44%	208	97.2%	170	99.4%	.105
	Yes	7	1.82%	6	2.8%	1	.6%	

Table 5. Number of Risk Factors

Number of Risk Factors		
Number of risk factors	No.	%
0	9	2.3%
1	71	18.4%
2	132	34.2%
3	116	30.1%
4	54	14.0%
5	3	.8%

Screening

The knowledge and attitude of CRC screening were assessed through 5 questions listed in Table 4. The majority of the participant (69.1%; n=266) didn't hear about CRC screening. Regarding the financial income, 46.2% (n=6) of people who had income >20000 SR had heard about CRC screening compared to 29.3% (n=44) of those with an income of <5000 SR. Similarly, regarding education level, whom didn't hear about CRC screening with intermediate education are 84.2% (n=16), while whom undergraduate and above are 66.3% (n=138).

The participants who aged 50 years or more 75.9% (n=22) they didn't get advised by their doctors to undergo CRC screening (P=.000). Most of the sample didn't know that CRC screening should be done at the age of 50 years 91.1% (n=351), the same for who aged 50 years or more 79.3% (n=23) (P=.003). Similarly, when it came to the financial income, participant with an income > 20000 SR 53.8% (n=7), compared to whom their income < 5000 SR 93.3% (n=140) (P=.000). The majority of the respondents didn't know how the CRC screening performed 59.7% (n=230), most of them are male

66% (n=142), the details of the screening questions listed in Table4. The participants perception about the educational programs of CRC screening in

Madinah shown as (53.91% (n=207) poor, 29.69% (n=114) low, 11.98% (n=46) good, and 4.69% (n=18) excellent).

Table 6. Participants Responses on CRC Screening

Questions		All		Sex				P Value
				Male		Female		
		No.	%	No.	%	No.	%	
Have you ever heard of CRC screening?	No	266	69.27%	149	69.6%	117	68.4%	.799
	Yes	119	30.99%	65	30.4%	54	31.6%	
Did your doctor advice you for CRC screening?	No	367	95.57%	202	94.4%	165	96.5%	.332
	Yes	18	4.69%	12	5.6%	6	3.5%	
At what age is CRC Screening performed?	At the age of 30 years	53	13.80%	34	15.9%	19	11.1%	.344
	At the age of 40 years	48	12.50%	27	12.6%	21	12.3%	
	At the age of 50 years	34	8.85%	14	6.5%	20	11.7%	
	At the presence of symptoms	67	17.45%	38	17.8%	29	17.0%	
	I don't know	183	47.66%	101	47.2%	82	48.0%	
How the CRC screening performed?	FOBT	77	20.05%	41	19.2%	36	21.1%	.022
	X_Ray	24	6.25%	15	7.0%	9	5.3%	
	CT-Scan	38	9.90%	29	13.6%	9	5.3%	
	Colonoscopy	178	46.35%	89	41.6%	89	52.0%	
	I Do Not Know	168	43.75%	98	45.8%	70	40.9%	
How do you rate the educational programs of CRC in Madinah?	Poor	207	53.91%	109	50.9%	98	57.3%	.004
	Low	114	29.69%	59	27.6%	55	32.2%	
	Good	46	11.98%	29	13.6%	17	9.9%	
	Excellent	18	4.69%	17	7.9%	1	.6%	

DISCUSSION:

According to the Saudi Cancer Registry (SCR) in 2014 the number of cases of CRC was 1,347 that newly diagnosed, which considered as 11.5% of all newly diagnosed cases among the Saudi population. Madinah was the sixth highest region in the number of CRC cases in Saudi Arabia. The Age-Standardised Incidence Rate (ASR) among Saudi males (per 100,000) was 10.0 / 100,000 and among Saudi females was 6.6 / 100,000.

This study was conducted to evaluate the awareness of CRC including knowledge, risk factors, and screening in Madinah population, in relation to age, sex, education level and financial situation.

As the highest knowledge score by the participants was 8 / 22, only half of the participants got 2 or 3, that mean that there is a significant defect of knowledge about CRC which can be explained by the responses on their perception of knowledge about it. For instance, limited knowledge and awareness of CRC was found in Ireland[8], Croatia[9]and between ethnic minority in the UK[10]. According to this, in 2007 Croatia created a national screening program to fill the gap of knowledge and screening awareness[9]. Similarly, in the Czech Republic, organized screening programs were implemented in 2000, and there has been a general trend of earlier CRC detection[11]. The majority of the participants didn't know that CRC is the second most common malignancy in

Saudi Arabia. Depending on the education level and its effect on the level of knowledge there was a significant difference that people with high level of education has better knowledge of CRC as they had heard about CRC and knew that it is the second most common malignancy in Saudi Arabia.

Overall, participants with more education have better knowledge of CRC. The same relation in the previous points appeared regarding the financial status as people with high income have better knowledge than those with low income.

As the majority of people found not knowing that CRC is more common in male, there was a significant difference between male and female as female were more knowledgeable that CRC is more common in male. Moreover, female were more knowledgeable about CRC which is not uncommon from the global perspective[7]. On the other hand, people with high income knew that CRC is more common in male than whom with low income.

Regarding the knowledge about signs and symptoms, less than half of the participants knew other CRC signs and symptoms other than continuous abdominal pain. A few of the participants thought that CRC has no symptoms. In another study, females were more knowledgeable of CRC symptoms[7].

Most of the sample thought that IBD is considered as a risk factor of CRC. People who aged 50 years or more showed the same association[7], while most of them didn't think that eating red meat is one of them, which correlate with the fact that daily eating red meat is the most common risk factor among Madinah population. More than half of the people who aged 50 years or more are at this risk. On the same relation with financial income, those with high income are consuming red meat more than with a lower income. Other studies showed that older participant aged 50 years and more knew that CRC family history considered as risk factor of CRC[7]. On the other hand, a family or relative history of CRC was the lowest risk factor found in the sample. Regarding consuming a sufficient amount of fruits and vegetables, we found that there was a significant relationship between increasing in age and having this healthy habit.

In our study, we chose 8 items of CRC risk factors to be measured. More than half of the participants had 2 or 3 risk factors. A few of them got the highest number of risk factors which was 5. That means that there is a different distribution of risk factors in the Madinah population.

The main risk factors for CRC include smoking, physical inactivity and eating processed meat [12]. We found that there is an increase in the number of the risk factors with the increasing of age.

People with high income have less risk factors compared to those with less income. The same relation appeared in the education level, participants with a high educational level have less risk factors compared to those with a lower educational level. There was an inverse correlation between the smoking and both of an increase in age and in financial income. In the meta analysis of 21 studies there was a significant reduction of CRC risk with regular physical activity[13].

In addition, there was an obvious relation between decreasing in regular physical activity and increasing of age. On the other hand, people who had a high education level are practicing regular physical activity more than people with lower education level.

The U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF) recommends screening for colorectal cancer using fecal occult blood testing, sigmoidoscopy, or colonoscopy in adults, beginning at age 50 years and continuing until age 75 years[14]. Most of the sample didn't hear about CRC screening, the age to perform it or the method of screening, which explained by participants perception about CRC screening educational programs in Madinah which they thought is poor. Another study showed that there is no difference in screening knowledge between male and female[15]. There was a significant relationship between the financial income and education level with the awareness of CRC screening. People who have a high education level and people who have a high income are aware of CRC screening more than those of lower education and low income. In other study, there is a significant association between higher education and higher income with cancer screening[16].

As getting old is one of the main CRC risk factors, we found that most of the people aged 50 years or more didn't get advice from their doctors to undergo CRC screening. People who aged 50 years or more and undergone CRC screening had more knowledge about CRC than whom weren't screening[15]. Based on the previous study and with correlation to ours, this explained that one of the causes of poor knowledge at this age group is due to poor screening programs in Saudi Arabia.

The majority of the sample and the majority of people aged 50 years or more didn't know that CRC screening was performed at 50 years of age. We noticed that people who had a high financial income

have been advised by their doctors to undergo a CRC screening more than those with low income. Some limitations of this study were that the sample biased towards younger participants and didn't represent of the exact demographics distribution in the Madinah population. Moreover, the goal of this study was to identify people with limited awareness of CRC (knowledge, screening) and the incidence of CRC risk factor among Madinah population, which was achieved successfully.

We encourage further studies to be done in the Madinah region that cover the screening behavior and its barriers

CONCLUSION:

There was a significant defect of knowledge regarding CRC among the population of Madinah. The higher the education level and income the more likely to have knowledge about CRC. Females was more knowledgeable than male. The most common risk factor for CRC in Madinah was eating red meat, and the lowest was a family or relative history of CRC. As there is increase in financial income and education level there is a decrease in the number of CRC risk factors and the opposite is true in regards age. Most of the population of Madinah have at least 2 or 3 risk factors for CRC. Most of the population of Madinah didn't hear about CRC screening, there is a relation between the higher education level and financial income and the more they hear about CRC screening. Most of those at the age of screening didn't undergo screening or were not advised by their doctors to undergo it. We recommend creating an educational and screening program for CRC that targets all the population and demographics in Madinah.

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Abbreviations

Age-Standardised Incidence Rate (ASR), Cancer Awareness Measure (CAM), Colorectal Cancer (CRC), Inflammatory Bowel Disease (IBD), Institutional Review Board (IRB), Saudi Cancer Registry (SCR), U.S. Preventive Services Task Force (USPSTF), World Health Organization (WHO).

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